

Non-Performing Assets in Indian Public and Private Sector Banks

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Abstract

This paper aims to identify and examine the factors that impact non-performing assets (NPAs), impede their proper observation, and propose suitable solutions to ensure their efficient monitoring and control. The banks chosen for this research are characterised by elevated Non-Performing Assets (NPAs) and are considered leading banks within their industry. Two of the three key priorities directly related to non-performing assets (NPAs) are identified and addressed in the Global Financial Stability Report of the International Monetary Fund (IMF, 2009): recapitalising weak but viable institutions and resolving failed institutions. This research study identifies the causes of non-performing loans by analysing a collection of 50 factors and develops the required metrics. The factor analysis test was conducted using the statistical software SPSS. The primary impetus to analyse and compare the factors influencing non-performing assets (NPAs) of public and private sector banks in India was the sectoral inequalities in the NPA ratio to advances in these banks. Factors contributing to non-performing assets (NPA) include infrequent engagement or follow-up with borrowers, manipulation of income or financial statements by borrowers, industrial issues, and the death of a family member who earns money.

Keywords: public and pvt. Sector, factor analysis, non-performing loans, metrics, financial statements etc.

Introduction

The non-performing assets (NPAs) of banks in India have become a significant concern, as a recurring occurrence of high-value loan defaults/cheats has contributed to the already high levels of NPAs in banks, especially public sector banks. They serve as a direct indicator of the performance of banks. Atypical levels of non-performing assets (NPAs) impact the profitability, overall assets, and liquidity of banks, while also posing a risk to the nature of their operations and driving them to the brink of indebtedness. Financial institutions are required to

maintain obligatory reserves, which diminishes the total earnings and ultimately the market worth of shares. Public sector banks offer financial assistance and loans to different sectors, taking into account the advantages and disadvantages, as well as the probability of recovering the borrowed funds without requiring collateral as security. The effective management of non-performing assets is crucial for ensuring the stability and growth of the banking industry in India. The Reserve Bank of India (RBI) observed an enhancement in the NPA management process, as banks effectively administered their NPA even after implementing credit time regulations of 90 days. (Agarwala 2019) Management of NPA is vital for the long-term sustainable growth of the banking sector with RBI and the Government of India. Strategies to manage non-performing assets (NPA) include implementing measures such as The Securitisation and Reconstruction of Financial Assets and Enforcement of Securities Interest Act, 2002 (which grants banks the authority to auction the residential or commercial properties of loan defaulters to recoup the loans), ensuring Capital Adequacy by Basel III Norms, and enforcing the Insolvency and Bankruptcy Code. To reduce the risks of non-performing assets (NPAs), the RBI advised banking institutions to enhance their credit standards, credit evaluation, and loan monitoring systems. To effectively manage non-performing assets (NPA), both preventative and remedial approaches are necessary. Proactive measures refer to the effective evaluation and management of loans, or NPA accounts, whereas curative methods concentrate on minimising the efforts required to resolve them. (Sharma et. al. 2019) The valuation methods of the bank must be refined during the disbursement phase. A realistic assessment of all technical, economic, commercial, organisational, and financial aspects of the project is necessary. The bankers should ensure that the project is technically and commercially viable, taking into account factors such as technical expertise, production scale, land acquisition, and so on. Certain initiatives are inherently flawed due to impractical planning, insufficient evaluation, and faulted execution.

The bank's profitability can significantly influence the effect of its non-performing assets (NPAs). The introduction of the Bankruptcy and Bankruptcy Code, 2016 has brought about significant changes in the bankruptcy laws of India, particularly with the incorporation of the corporate insolvency resolution process methodology. Through the introduction of this novel strategy, the attention was somewhat redirected towards achieving a harmonious equilibrium between the requirements of the company and the "operational creditor" (a newly coined term encompassing the former secured creditors, employees, and unsecured creditors

all under one umbrella term), instead of simply liquidating and allocating the remaining assets of a company burdened by debt among its creditors in a hierarchy of importance. The objective of this novel strategy was to intentionally manage the debt to reduce the risk for all the parties concerned in the scenario.

Review of Literature

Researchers have recognised the significance of proficient management of non-performing assets and credit standards or policies as a subject of academic inquiry. Scholars have endeavoured to conduct empirical studies on the management of non-performing assets in banks, both domestically and internationally. The research findings of several published studies are presented below. In their 2013 study, Pestova and Mamonov examined the credit risk of Russian banks using single-equation panel data models. They analyzed macroeconomic and bank-specific indicators and observed that the increase in interest rates contributes to the acceleration of bad assets growth. Sontakke and Tiwari (2013) emphasised that Non-Performing Assets (NPA) have captured significant attention as a major issue for Indian banks following the reform in financial sectors. Net Non-Performing Assets (NPA) impact profitability as banks are unable to generate money from them, leading to higher provisions and funding costs. The economy can be significantly impacted by inadequate handling of NPA. They proposed suitable strategies to manage or reduce non-performing assets (NPAs).

In their 2015 study, Manab, Theng, and Md-Rus examined the relationship between earnings management and credit default prediction in Malaysia. They found that critical determinants of credit risk are the liquidity ratios, productivity ratio, and profitability ratio. In their study, Laveena and Kumar (2016) determined that India's non-performing asset (NPA) level in the banking sector continues to be elevated in comparison to global benchmarks. Bardhan and Mukherjee (2016) noted that the capital adequacy ratio serves as a prudential measure for the non-performing assets (NPAs) of banks. They also found that larger banks are more susceptible to default compared to smaller banks. Moreover, the elimination of non-performing assets (NPAs) can be achieved by enhancing the profitability of banks. The practice of modifying conventional advances gives rise to a moral hazard issue and allows borrowers to claim that projects have failed as a result of exceptional circumstances. The official NPA statistics, which measure the ratio of gross NPAs to gross advances, fail to adequately reflect the significant loan delinquencies in banks (Samantaraya, 2016).

This research paper seeks to examine the correlation between non-performing loans and the GDP growth rate in Kenya through an analysis of the macroeconomic environment from 1980 to 2015. In conclusion, the researcher asserts that the macroeconomic environment and its support are crucial factors in the successful monitoring of non-performing loans. Muthami (2016) A study conducted by Meher (2017) examines the effects of the government's note bandi decision on the non-performing assets (NPA) of Indian banks during the post-demonetization period. A comprehensive analysis of the events in the banking sector reveals both advantageous and disadvantageous aspects.

Sengupta and Vardhan (2017) have conducted a comparative analysis of two major banking crisis events that occurred following liberalisation. The first episode occurred in the late 1990s, while the second episode began after the 2008 global financial crisis, which brought attention to the problem of non-performing assets (NPAs). The authors argue that implementing robust governance, aggressive banking regulatory measures, and a robust legal framework for resolving non-performing assets (NPAs) would help address the issue of NPAs. In contrast, regulatory forbearance would hurt the banking crisis. Mishra and Pawaskar (2017) have advised that banks should implement a robust credit evaluation system to prevent non-performing assets (NPAs). They argue that the issue of non-performing assets (NPAs) can be resolved by implementing a suitable regulatory framework to assist banks in debt collection.

In their 2017 study, Sahni and Seth examine the specific factors contributing to the increasing Non-Performing Assets (NPAs) and the effects on bank operations. The authors have outlined many preventative and therapeutic strategies to manage non-performing assets (NPAs). They have proposed that a thorough evaluation of the borrower's creditworthiness should be conducted to guarantee prompt loan recovery. Mittal and Suneja (2017) conducted an analysis of the magnitude of non-performing assets (NPAs) in the banking industry of India and the factors that have contributed to the increase in NPAs. They propose that while the government has implemented several measures to mitigate the issue of non-performing assets (NPAs), bankers should also take a proactive approach in embracing well-designed policies to effectively handle NPAs. The approval of the loan should be based on a thorough evaluation of the projected project's return on investment and the repayment capacity of the clients.

To investigate the impact of gross non-performing assets (NPAs) and net NPAs on the asset quality of private sector banks and public sector banks, Banerjee, Verma, and Jaiswal

(2018) conducted a literature review. The primary factors contributing to the accumulation of non-performing assets (NPAs) include intentional loan defaults, inadequate credit management practices, and the approval of loans without considering the borrowers' risk-bearing capacity. Banking institutions should prioritise the development and effective implementation of more robust strategies. Rigorous measures implemented by the government could effectively decrease the amount of non-performing assets (NPAs).

Mukhopadhyay (2018) has examined the issues surrounding India's non-performing assets (NPAs) and has proposed potential remedies. He proposed that to address the issues of non-performing assets (NPAs), the Reserve Bank of India (RBI) should not adhere to a uniform model. Instead, it should adopt a creative and adaptable strategy tailored to each bank, taking into account their unique circumstances.

In their 2018 study, Kumar, Subba Rao, and Kusuma investigate the primary factors contributing to the accumulation of non-performing assets (NPAs). The primary factors identified are economic downturn, shifts in government policy, inadequate credit assessment system, intentional defaults, and flaws in the lending process. In a new research analysis, Dey (2018) examines the recovery component of non-performing loans in Indian commercial banks. The author considers the function of DRTs to be far superior to the process of recovery facilitated by Lok Adalats and the SARFASEI Act.

In their 2019 study, Sharma, Rathore, and Prasad emphasised that the primary function of a banking system is to provide loans to businesses or borrowers seeking to invest or expand. Extending loans to businesses carries a Credit Risk, which is the possibility of the borrower failing to meet its contractual commitments either during transactions or in the future. Failure of the banking industry has a detrimental effect on other sectors as well. Upon considering research papers, we identified a significant need for researching the factors that contribute to Non-Performing Assets (NPA) using primary and empirical methods. Our goal is to propose strategies for credit risk management in India. Non-performing assets (NPAs) cannot be completely eradicated, however, measures such as the Bankruptcy Code can be pursued to decrease and retrieve non-performing loans by efficient execution. In their 2019 study, Agarwala, V. and Agarwala, N. found that the growth rate of non-performing assets (NPAs) in the Indian banking sector is comparatively lower than that of nationalised banks, as well as the State Bank of India (SBI) and its affiliated entities. The ineffective management of the problem

of poor loans by the nationalised banks and associate banks of SBI has resulted in a remarkable surge in the growth of such loans.

The loan flow to different sectors of the economy is augmenting. Sectors primarily include infrastructure, agriculture, services, and industry. The majority of research articles focus on topics such as Non-Performing Assets (NPAs) in both public sector and private sector banks, including the causes of NPAs and strategies to address the NPA problem. No study was undertaken to assess the extent of gross bank credit deployment by main sectors and the corresponding number of non-performing assets (NPAs) generated by each sector. In addition, we can examine the causes of the Non-Performing Assets (NPA) in each sector and devise sector-specific solutions to address the issue. The identification of the most troublesome sector enables us to implement appropriate corrective measures.

The aims of the research are as follows:

- To identify and assess the causes contributing to non-performing assets (NPA)
- The objectives of this study are to propose several strategies for managing non-performing assets (NPAs) and to assess the financial performance of chosen public sector banks and private sector banks in India using relevant ratios and the CAMEL model from 2008 to 2018.

The present study aims to compare the many dimensions that influence the non-performing assets of banks in India. The selected bank branches for the study have a higher Non-Performing Asset (NPA) exposure. The collection of primary data for this study was conducted using questionnaires and direct engagements with bank personnel. Statistical sampling was employed to get the data from the middle-level managers. This study endeavours to identify the factors contributing to non-performing loans by analysing a collection of 50 variables and proposing the essential strategies for managing NPAs. Data obtained from questionnaires was compiled into tables.

Banks in India

In addition to credit institutions, the Indian banking system has 27 public sector banks, 21 private sector banks, 49 foreign banks, 56 rural regional banks, 1562 municipal cooperative banks, and 94,384 rural cooperative banks. After the second quarter of 2012, the aggregate credit provided by commercial banks amounted to 90,579.89 billion rupees (\$1,290.68 billion),

while deposits increased to \$118,501.82 billion. The total value of assets held by public sector banks was 1,557.04 billion. Financial institutions in India are progressively prioritising the implementation of a comprehensive strategy for managing risks. Financial institutions have previously embraced the Basel II International Banking Supervision Agreement, and the majority of banks are currently adhering to the Basel III capital standards, which will cease to be effective on March 31, 2019. The Reserve Bank of India (RBI) has announced its intention to establish a public credit registry (PCR), which will act as a complete database of credit information accessible to all parties involved. A modification to the Ordinance on the Insolvency and Bankruptcy Code, a draft legislation for 2017, has been approved to enhance the banking industry.

Banks extend loans to various classes of borrowers, each at their level of risk. In addition to funds obtained from the market - equities and debt - they provide loans from public deposits. Engagement in mediation activities exposes the bank to a multitude of dangers. Documented instances of significant bank failures resulting from their failure to manage risk exposures are easily accessible. To mitigate the risk of non-recovery, banks are required to set aside a specific proportion of their capital as collateral. The Basel Committee has formulated a set of regulations known as Basel norms for banking to address risk. Basel is a principal city located in Switzerland. As the headquarters of the BIS, it facilitates collaboration among central banks aiming to achieve financial stability and establish unified banking rules. Bi-monthly, the BIS convenes a meeting with the governor and high-ranking officials from the central banks of the member states. The Basel guidelines are comprehensive supervision standards developed by intergovernmental organisations of central banks known as the Basel Committee on Banking Supervision (BCBS). The Basel/Basel provision refers to the set of regulations within the BCBS Agreement that primarily address the risks faced by banks and the financial system. The objective of the agreement is to guarantee that financial institutions maintain an adequate amount of capital to cover their obligations and avoid unforeseen losses. India has implemented the Basel Banking Regulations. Indeed, based on many criteria, the RBI has established more rigorous standards in comparison to the standards mandated by the BCBS.

In 1988, BCBS implemented a capital measurement scheme known as the Basel Capital Accord, typically referred to as Basel I. It places virtually exclusive emphasis on credit risk. The statement delineates the capital and risk weights structure adopted by banks. The

mandatory minimum capital is established at 8% of the risk-weighted assets (RWA). RWA refers to assets categorised by their distinct risk profiles. Bank assets were categorised into five groups based on credit risk, as indicated by risk weights of 0% (for instance, cash a home country debt like treasuries); 20% (securitisations such as MBS rated AAA); 50%; 100%; – some assets were assigned no rating. (Sarkar & Sarkar 2018)

The Basel II rules, made available by the BCBS in 2004, were seen as enhanced and revised iterations of the Basel Agreement. The guidelines were derived from three specific criteria: 1. Financial institutions must uphold a minimum capital adequacy threshold of 8% of high-risk assets. Banks must enhance and implement more effective risk management strategies in the surveillance and control of all three categories of hazards. 3. It is imperative for banks to declare their level of risk and other relevant information to the central bank.

Basel III, which was released in December 2010, is the third accord in the Basel Convention series. Introducing these principles was a direct response to the 2008 financial crisis. These accords specifically deal with the risk management elements of the banking activity. Basel III is the worldwide regulatory framework governing banks' capital adequacy, stress tests, and market liquidity risk requirements. It enhances the banking sector's capacity to absorb shocks resulting from financial and economic stress, irrespective of their origin; enhances risk management and governance; reinforces bank transparency and disclosure standards.

The Code of Insolvency and Bankruptcy The Insolvency and Bankruptcy Code (IBC), 2016 is the Indian legislation governing bankruptcy. Its purpose is to streamline the current framework by establishing a unified scheme for insolvency services. The Bankruptcy Code is a measure to temporarily halt bankruptcy proceedings, which is now a protracted procedure and does not provide a financially feasible resolution. A robust insolvency framework in India that aims to minimise both the costs and timing of insolvency proceedings. The implementation of the Code will effectively safeguard the interests of small investors and streamline the entrepreneurial process. Bankruptcy is a legal condition typically enforced by a court due to the inability of a corporation or an individual to fulfil their debt responsibilities. The recent bankruptcy legislation in India aims to establish a structured insolvency resolution procedure (IRP) for enterprises, either by establishing a feasible means of survival or by guaranteeing their prompt liquidation. When the Insolvency Resolution Process (IRP) is implemented,

creditors' petitions are rendered inactive for 180 days. During this time, they will be presented with proposals for revival and will determine their next steps. During these 180 days, a minimum of 75% of creditors must consent to a revival plan. Insufficient attainment of this minimum criterion results in the company being thrust into liquidation. If a majority of the creditors, totalling three-quarters, determine that the case is complex and cannot be resolved within a period of 180 days, the judge has the authority to provide a single extension of up to 90 days for the trial.

Year	Gross Advances	Gross NPAs
2013	40560	1559
2014	45704.5838	2167.3920
2015	48452.70	2627.45
2016	50821.49	5020.70
2017	51422.28	6410.58

Table 1. Public sector banks

Figure 1. Public sector banks (2013-2017)

The data from 2013 to 2017 reveals a notable trend in the performance of public sector banks in India, particularly regarding gross advances and gross non-performing assets (NPAs). In 2013, the gross advances were 40,560, with gross NPAs at 1,559. As the years progressed, the gross advances showed a steady increase, reaching 51,422.28 in 2017. This upward trend in gross advances indicates that public sector banks consistently expanded their lending activities during this period.

However, alongside this increase in gross advances, there is a significant rise in gross NPAs, which represent the loans that are not being repaid as expected. In 2014, gross NPAs grew to 2,167.39 from the previous year's 1,559, and this growth continued sharply in the following years. By 2016, gross NPAs had surged to 5,020.70, and in 2017, they escalated further to 6,410.58. This rapid increase in NPAs highlights a growing challenge for public sector banks, as a higher proportion of their lending portfolio became non-performing, indicating potential issues with credit quality and financial stability. The disparity between the

growth of advances and the even more rapid increase in NPAs suggests that while banks were expanding their loan books, they also faced escalating difficulties in ensuring repayment, reflecting broader economic and sectoral challenges.

Conclusion

The analysis indicates significant advancements in both the chosen prominent public and private sector banks over the given research timeframe. The analysis of CAMEL's ratings reveals that, in terms of overall group performance and performance consistency, the chosen public sector banks outperformed the chosen private sector banks. Indian Public Sector Banks (PSBs) should enhance their efficiency in asset management policy, employee performance, cost control, and customer-friendly banking operations to match the rigorous performance of private sector banks in India and compete with international players. Several factors that can influence non-performing assets include the type of loan, the creditworthiness of borrowers, collateral security, lack of proper monitoring, inadequacy in credit assessment criteria, death of a working family member, and business failure/absence of entrepreneurial information on the borrower's side. The current loan application methodology for high-net-worth individuals and corporate entities is riddled with vulnerabilities that can be readily manipulated by unscrupulous firms in collaboration with corrupt bank personnel. Financial institutions have failed to adequately adopt the necessary information technology tools that enable the Basel II/III standards for risk management, resulting in regulatory shortcomings. The loan categories with a greater likelihood of non-performing assets are personal loans, housing loans, and school loans. Before approving a loan, it is important to analyse aspects such as the borrowers' overall income, creditworthiness, and past credit records or loan settlement history. Some causes of non-performing assets (NPA) include infrequent contact or follow-up with borrowers, intentional manipulation of income or financial statements by borrowers, industrial issues, and the death of a family member who earns money. Aspects such as downsizing the workforce to reduce expenses, diversifying work tasks, increased workload, and insufficient efforts by credit managers or branch managers may impede the efficient approval and monitoring of loans. Crucial strategies for decreasing non-performing assets (NPAs) include ongoing communication with debtors, participation in lok adalat, reaching compromise settlements, and securitising assets.

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